

A Study of Top 14 GDP Countries' Spending Patterns

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Overview

This is a study on the top 14 countries with the highest average GDP over the course of five years (2013-2017). The goal is to reveal meaningful patterns by using data visualization, and to underline trends that will otherwise be ignored. In the research process, three major spending categories were studied and explored to speculate the economic growth in the selected countries.

Top 14 GDP
Country Overall
Spending in
Billions (\$)
2017

The most recent available data shows US has the highest spending (17238 B) overall while being followed closely by China(11778 B).

Spending Per Capita in Billions (\$)

This chart is ranked by the amount of spending per capita in 2017 while Australia leads the ranking as the highest spender in 2017, it also has the highest average spending from 2013 to 2017. US no longer is the top spender by capita, proving that spending behavior can be varied by population.

Total Spending vs GDP in Billions (\$) 2017

To introduce more variables that could help explaining spending trend, we can take a closer look on how GDP could be compared to spending. In most recent year, 2017, all 14 countries have higher GDP than spending except Japan, which overspent the countries' market value of all the final goods and services produced annually.

Spending Comparisons

The following graphs examine dollar spent by category, and by average the top 14 countries spend the most on healthcare and the least on military.

Education Spending

Education expenditure as share of GDP in %

Education expenditure per capita as share of GDP per capita in %

The trend of education expenditure as share of GDP vs per capita spending is almost identical among nations. Brazil has the highest education expenditure out of its GDP while Japan and India have the lowest. This trend no longer apply to per capita education expenditure, UK becomes the highest spender per capita while India surged its spending from 2014 and onward.

Healthcare Spending

Healthcare expenditure as share of GDP in %

Healthcare expenditure per capita as share of GDP per capita in %

With more completed data, healthcare expenditure among nations are more consistent in comparing to education. The per capita is very similar to the overall healthcare expenditure in relation to GDP.

Military Spending

Military expenditure as share of GDP in %

Military expenditure per capita as share of GDP per capita in %

With more completed data, military expenditure among nations are more consistent. The per capita is almost identical to the overall military expenditure in relation to GDP. It is not a surprise that Saudi Arabia spend the most on military out of its GDP, followed up by Russia.

Education growth rate in percent and fixed values

- In terms of education growth, Germany and US have the highest increase in 2014 while Japan declined in the same year. From 2015 and onward there are no significant jump or decline in education expenditure.
- By percent of growth, fluctuation is more significant. India increased the most in 2015 in rate of growth while Brazil declined. Rates are mostly tending towards growth from 2016 and onward.

Healthcare growth rate in percent and fixed values

- For Healthcare, US and China experienced the highest increase in 2015 and decline in 2016 while Saudi Arabia has the most fluctuated rate of growth.

GDP vs Spending

- This bubble graph above displays bubble size in terms of population size. There is a vivid direct relation between GDP and total spending, the higher the GDP the more likely it is for countries to spend. However, it is less impact by population size, while being the most populated country, China is behind US in spending and GDP.

GDP vs Population

- There is no significant correlation between population and GDP. However, the more populated nations tend to generate more GDP. The size of the bubble is determined by total spending.
- It is also expected there are no abnormal proportion in spending vs GDP. Spending have significant share in percent of GDP in all countries studied.

Education vs Healthcare

- Education expenditure per capita is directly related to healthcare expenditure. It is likely for someone to be more aware of personal care or healthcare when one acquires more education. The size of the bubble is determined by GDP per capita.

Healthcare vs Military

- Healthcare expenditure per capita is not related to military expenditure while US stands out as an outlier to be the biggest spender in both categories.

Education vs Military

- Education expenditure per capita is not related to military expenditure while US stands out as an outlier to be the biggest spender in both categories.

Conclusion

This is a study aims to reveal the spending patterns of top 14 nations with highest average GDP over the year of 2013 to 2017. In exploring the data, three major spending categories were studied to measure economic growth in the selected countries:

- Education
 - A category with most missing data from China, Saudi Arabia, Russia and Canada. The remaining data reveals Australia as the highest average education expenditure.
 - In the year of 2014 to 2015 the rate of education expenditure fluctuates the most both in percent and fixed value.
 - Education expenditure is directly related to healthcare expenditure per capita, suggesting that the more educated an individual the more like he/she is willing to invest in personal care.
- Healthcare
 - With the most complete data, healthcare is ranked the highest spending category out of the three studied while US is the leading spending country in this category.
- Military
 - Saudi Arabia is the leading country that invested the most in military.
 - Military spending as a percent of GDP has almost identical distributions as it is per capita, suggesting that individual impact on military expenditure closely mirrors national wide distribution.
 - It is also the category with the least average investment in years studies among the selected countries.
- Spending in relation to GDP and Population
 - It is expected there are no abnormal proportion in spending vs GDP. Spending have significant share in percent of GDP in all countries studied.
 - There is no significant relation in population vs GDP. US leads the total GDP with considerable lower population.

Overall, US is still the country with the most prominent economic growth in terms of its spending patterns and the value of GDP. However, the research is limited by missing education data, and other expenditure categories should also be considered in order to generate more substantial outcomes.

Reference

- World Bank Open Data
- <https://data.worldbank.org/> Google Charts
- <https://developers.google.com/chart/interactive/docs/Contact>
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